

Pyrylium Salts and *Spiro*-Dipyrans. Part II. Condensation Products from Methyleneethyl ketone and *o*-Hydroxy Aldehydes.

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In Part I (this *Volume*, p. 23) it was shown that α -alkylated acetoacetic ester condenses with *o*-hydroxy aldehydes to form *o*-hydroxy styryl benzo-(or naphtho)-pyrylium salts. In the present communication are recorded the results of the action of methyleneethyl ketone on *o*-hydroxyaldehydes. In these the reactions of methyleneethylketone closely resemble those of the α -alkylated acetoacetic ester. The reaction proceeds in two stages as before (*loc. cit.*). In the first stage one molecule of the aldehyde condenses with one of the ketone to produce a pyrylium salt. In the second stage this salt condenses with another molecule of the aldehydes to yield an *o*-hydroxy styryl benzo-(or naphtho)-pyrylium salt. But the presence of two reactive groups in methyleneethyl ketone may admit of two possible reactions (a) and (b), as shown in the following formulae :

Under the condition (experimental part) the reaction takes the course (a): the hydroxy styryl benzopyrylium chloride resulting from salicylaldehyde and methyleneethyl ketone is identical with the 3-methyl 2-(*o*-hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium chloride (III a) derived from

salicylaldehyde and 2:3-dimethylbenzo-pyrylium chloride (II a); also the pyrylium salt obtained from β -naphthol- α -aldehyde is the same whether methylethyl ketone or α -methyl acetoacetic ester is used.

The pyrylium salts are decomposed by alkali into colourless pseudo-bases which, on heating with hydrochloric acid, are converted into the pyrylium salts again. The *spiro*-dinaphthopyrone undergoes a colour change from white to blue-violet when heated with solvents, such as benzene, toluene and alcohol, which disappears again on cooling,—a property which is absent in the *spiro*-dibenzopyrans.

Attempts to prepare compounds having the formulae (IIb, IIIb) are being made by a different method and will be described in a subsequent communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3-Methyl-2-(α -hydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium Chloride (IIIa).

Into a mixture of salicylaldehyde (20 g.) and methylethylketone (6.0 g.) dissolved in ether (50 c.c.) hydrogen chloride gas was passed. The solution at once turned deep red and after a few minutes crystals began to separate. The hydrochloric acid gas was passed till the mixture was filled with a thick paste of crystals. This was filtered and washed with ether. Crystallised from acetic acid in dark needles having a metallic lustre, it has the melting point 198°. It was dried over caustic potash in vacuum and analysed. (Found: Cl, 11.62. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2Cl$ requires Cl, 11.89 per cent.).

The *ferric salt* can be obtained in red colour from the acetic acid solution of ferric chloride and the pyrylium chloride. The *perchlorate* can similarly be obtained by adding perchloric acid.

3-Methyl-spiro-dibenzopyran.

By adding ammonia to the aqueous solution of the pyrylium chloride, the pseudo-base was obtained as a white product, mixed

with tarry matter. It was purified by crystallisation from ligroin; m.p. 80°. (Found: C, 82.12; H, 5.56. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 82.4 H, 5.64 per cent.).

3-Methyl-7-hydroxy-2-(2': 4'-dihydroxystyryl)-benzopyrylium Chloride.

In a solution of resorcyaldehyde (8 g.) and methylethylketone (2 g.) dissolved in ether (20 c.c.) hydrochloric acid gas was passed till the mixture was saturated with the gas. Within a short time the solution assumed a violet colour and was filled with highly coloured crystals. After several hours' standing the crystals were filtered and washed with ether. Crystallised from acetic acid it forms green-violet crystals with a metallic lustre, m.p. 290°. It was dried in vacuum over caustic potash and analysed. (Found: Cl, 10.84. $C_{18}H_{14}O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 10.74 per cent.).

From the acetic acid solution of the chloride, the *ferric salt* can be obtained by adding ferric chloride as violet-red needles.

3-Methyl-7:7'-dihydroxy-spiro-dibenzopyran.

The colourless base was obtained by shaking the chloride with aqueous ammonia and was crystallised from alcohol. On heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid it was converted into the coloured chloride. (Found: C, 78.21; H, 4.92. $C_{18}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 78.47; H, 4.76 per cent.).

3-Methyl-2-(o-hydroxy- α -benzostyryl)- β -naphtho-pyrylium Chloride.

It was obtained from β -naphthol- α -aldehyde (11 g.) and methyl-ethylketone (2.4 g.) dissolved in acetic acid on saturating the solution with hydrochloric acid gas. After about 2 days the chloride separated in green crystals with a metallic lustre. This was filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from acetic acid and dried over caustic potash in vacuum. It did not melt at 290° . (Found: C, 77.97; H, 4.35. $C_{26}H_{19}O_2Cl$ requires C, 78.29; H, 4.76 per cent.)

The ferric salt can be obtained in greenish-red colour by adding ferric chloride to the acetic acid solution of the chloride.

3-Methyl-spiro-dinaphthopyran.

It was obtained by decomposing the chloride with ammonia. The impure product was purified from benzene when it formed colourless crystals, m.p. 201° . (Found: C, 86.28; H, 5.21. $C_{26}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 86.15; H, 5.02 per cent.)

On heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid the pseudo-base is converted into the coloured chloride. On warming with benzene, toluene and alcohol it undergoes a colour change from white to blue-violet which disappears again on cooling.

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